

Translation as Storytelling: Ecological Narratives in *Planet Earth III* Re-Narrated for Chinese Audiences

Xinzuo LI

School of Foreign Languages and Cultures, Nanjing Normal University, China.
Email: 1056778785@qq.com; xinzuo@nnu.edu.cn

Abstract

Recent decades have witnessed the mushrooming of documentary films evidenced by the prevalence of BBC nature documentary series across the globe. Amongst them, Planet Earth series serve as a notable example, in which Sir David Attenborough as the narrator demonstrates through his commentaries the wonders of nature and its inhabitants. Thus, documentaries as such fall into the categories of ecological narratives. In audio-visual translation (AVT), the primary focus of subtitling, dubbing and voice-over is to transform those narratives as the source text (ST) into the target text (TT), which means re-narration does from time to time happen. This paper delves into *Diqiumaidong III 地球脉动第三季*, the Chinese version of Planet Earth III (2023), and analyses how ecological narratives are reaccentuated for the Chinese audiences. Through the lens of Baker's socio-narrative theory, the paper finds that selective appropriation, framing by labelling and repositioning are adopted in the Chinese version of the nature documentary. In so doing, animal behaviours, environmental changes, human-animal conflicts and other ecology-rated issues are revealed more directly to raise ecological awareness of the general public in China. The papers also shed some lights for retelling stories through translation practices, particularly AVT and multimodal translation.

Keywords: *Ecological Narratives; Socio-Narrative Translation; Narrative Approach; Reframing and Re-Narrating; Planet Earth III.*

1. INTRODUCTION

With the burgeoning of modern photography equipment and techniques, the documentary film has become a world-wide hit medium due to its unparalleled magic of demonstrating in a simple yet unprecedented way ideas, objects and creatures, especially those mysterious albeit complicated in the eyes of humans. But some of those things exist only in ancient papers or even are intangible. Others might be alive but do not speak any language at all, or at least, do not speak languages that humans can understand. Then, it is up to we humanities and humanities alone to record their lives and adapt these stories in acceptable and even enlightening ways. In that process, an individual narrator, or in some cases several, becomes an essential part of filming documentaries. That thus defines documentary films as a type of narratives.

Of all the documentaries, nature documentaries, also known as wildlife documentaries, are in their essence narratives to the greatest extent. Unlike their historical counterparts with strong indispositions towards certain events or so-called facts, nature documentaries centres around animals, plants and other living creatures apart from humans, creatures that do not have an opinion themselves, and therefore relies most heavily on filmmakers to present narratives and weaves stories that offer a glimpse of their lives in the natural world. In that sense, it can be said that nature documentaries and nature itself are reciprocal. On the one hand, the main

mission of nature documentaries is to record, represent and interpret the natural world with narratives so that humanities can appreciate the natural beauties, reflect on human-environment relations and put wrongs to rights for the welfare of all living creatures. On the other hand, the natural world inserts with its diversity and dynamism great impetus into the filming process. On and on, nature documentaries reinforce the natural world and vice versa.

But this also solicits wide criticism around the concept “narratives”. For some, narratives of this type are purposefully condensed from footage over a long period of time and are “constructed to be as compelling as possible” (Lopez 2017). That is to say, stories in which animals survive and thrive might be based on pure fabrication for entertainment or other purposes. In this paper, the veracity of the so-called naturalness in these narratives are not to be questioned nonetheless. What is to be examined, however, is the exact language, or ST, selected by the narrator to complete a whole story.

When a nature documentary gains international popularity and wants to be introduced in a transnational context, audio-visual translation (AVT), in which “interlingual subtitling” “dubbing” and “voice-over” (Gambier 2003, 172) are the most important and dominant typologies, becomes means of cross-cultural communication. As Delabastita (1989) divides AVT modes into four types, namely the verbal (stylistic and dialectical features), the literary and theatrical (elements appropriate to the genre), the proxemic and kinetic (non-verbal behaviours in general), and the cinematic (camera and filming technique), he points to the nature of AVT, that is, multimodal. This means that elements other than the linguistic meanings of ST should also be taken into account, which includes “translation procedures as well as their socio-cultural and historical context” (Munday *et al.* 2022, 235). In this context, translating nature documentaries for foreign audiences necessarily involves re-narrating the existing narratives in ST, which would produce TT whose re-narrated narratives might not be the same as those presented in ST.

To further figure out how AVT in nature documentaries functions as re-narration, the paper investigates *Planet Earth III (2023)* and its Chinese version and aims to find out how ecological narratives are re-rendered for the Chinese audiences.

2. PLANET EARTH SERIES IN GENERAL AND *PLANET EARTH III (2023)* IN PARTICULAR

Planet Earth series is a nature documentary franchise produced by the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC), following its blockbuster and landmark series *The Blue Planet¹* (2001), which concentrates on the world’s oceans and maritime lives in the planet. Since the latter received critical acclaim from the market, the BBC decided to repeat the formula by filming another series dedicated to the planet as a whole, which brought to the BBC Natural History Unit the very idea of filming *Planet Earth*.

Commissioned in 2001 by Lorraine Heggessey², the then BBC One Controller, *Planet Earth* finally made its debut in 2006. As of 2023, the documentary franchise has spawned three main series, several spinoff TV series and feature films. In particular, the three main seasons are briefly introduced for better understandings of the series. *Planet Earth (2006)*, the first of its kind, was the most expensive nature documentary ever commissioned by the BBC and the first to be recorded in high definition (Slenske 2007). Five years in making, it has eleven fifty-minute episodes covering poles, mountains, fresh waters, caves, deserts, plains, jungles, forests, seas, oceans and basically all types of biomes on the planet. In this season, the

audiences are allowed access to breathtaking landscapes and diversity of species on the earth. Following its predecessor, *Planet Earth II* (2016) was distributed as a sequel to the previous 2006 series by BBC Wildlife and was the first BBC TV series to produced in ultra high definition. It continues the BBC's exploration of the planet in six episodes and manages to film some of the world's most inaccessible areas and specifically record wildlife in grasslands, islands and cities for the first time in this series.

As the recent sequel, *Planet Earth III* (2023) is the third installment of the series. For this season, the production crews travelled to and filmed in forty-three countries and six continents during the past five years, some shoots were managed remotely online in quarantine during the COVID-19 pandemic, and latest and niche technologies, some previously restricted for military use only or developed exclusively for this series, were adapted in the filming process, thus capturing for the first time some rare species and their peculiar behaviours. In total, it has eight episodes, but the way that it tells stories are rather different. Instead of focusing on how animals exist alone, this season pays great attention as to how they can get along with one dominant species, human beings. Each and every one of animals filmed is woven into a rhetoric or scenario, in which how they survive and thrive is contextualised into different relationships, which can be but are not necessarily antagonised. Parents vs. children, senior vs. junior, predator vs. prey, parasite vs. victim, partner vs. troublemaker, humans vs. animals ... All these demonstrate different narratives adapted in the series. Also, this season prioritises the question of coexistence between humans and wildlife by observing changes in ecosystems, be they subtle or overt, caused by climate change, global warming, rise of sea level and other human activities. Human endeavours to save the planet and rare species are demonstrated throughout as well.

In a word, *Planet Earth III* (2023) offers a panoramic view of human-wildlife relations on the earth and encompasses abundant resources for studying how ecological awareness are aroused and depicted. All these cannot do without the power of narratives contained, which are dictated to the audiences through the lips of Sir David Attenborough³ as the narrator. A great biologist and wildlife enthusiast, Sir David manages to connect the audiences with the natural world through his fascinating commentaries and captivating voice. His unique understandings and interpretations of the natural world, or more simply his narratives, has ensured the ubiquitous popularity of natural documentaries epitomised by *Planet Earth III* (2023).

Likewise in China, Sir David is in no shortage of fans. His international fame and life-long devotion to nature has ensured that *Planet Earth III* (2023) goes viral among Chinese audiences as quickly as its predecessors. Even it is re-edited as a feature film⁴. In terms of the Chinese version itself, *Planet Earth III* (2023) is introduced into the Chinese market by Docu TV⁵ as *Diqiumaidong III 地球脉动第三季*. Later, it is broadcasted via various media platforms in China.

In the Chinese version, the original narratives in English produced by Sir David are replaced by mandarin, spoken by Liu Cong⁶, a famous Chinese dubber. Although the exact translator or translators of the narratives cannot be traced, Liu's dubbing gives the Chinese audiences a vivid picture of how wildlife make their lives in the documentary. Therefore, the (re)narratives in Chinese to be analysed are based on the transcripts of Liu's narration. But before elaborating on these (re)narratives, an overview of narrative theory should be provided to serve as the guiding principle.

3. SOCIO-NARRATIVE THEORY

Drawing on the notion from the field of sociology and communication, rather than narratology or linguistics, Baker (2006, 3) defines narratives as “everyday stories we live by”. In that sense, the notion of narratives, or what Baker would call stories, becomes indeed “a highly transparent and intuitively concept” (Ibid) that even laymen can understand. Later, Baker (2018, 19) concretises the definition by restricting the scope of stories to “public and personal”. This brings to her typology of narratives, which includes four types, namely ontological narratives, public narratives, conceptual/disciplinary narratives and meta-narratives. As illustrative in their own rights, the first two types focus on stories elaborated respectively by certain individuals and by social or public institutions, while disciplinary narratives are related to scholarly explanations in specific zones and meta-narratives, also known as master or grand narratives, refer to “narratives in which we are embedded as contemporary actors in history” (Somers & Gibson 1994, 61) or “the epic dramas of our time” (Somers 1992, 605). In terms of nature documentaries, narratives contained are obviously public, as they represent the endeavours of the media and of the circles of ecologists, biologists and environmentalists to protect the one and only planet on which humans and wildlife dwell.

To further unveil the intricacies of narratives and mechanisms behind them, Baker (2006 51, 61, 67, 71) builds upon the previous framework laid out by Somers and Gibson and comes up with the features of narratives, among which the most important of all are “temporality”, “relationality”, “causal emplotment”, and “selective appropriation”. While temporality indicates that narratives are often construed temporally and spatially, relationality points to the fact that a narrative cannot be coherent without the balance of events or elements within events (Baker 2010). Unlike relationality which means the interpretation of events within a larger configuration of events, casual emplotment emphasises “independent events” and overrides “their chronological and categorical order” (Somers 1997, 82). In Baker’s word (*Narratives* 8), casual emplotment means “making moral sense of events”, in which opinions and attitudes towards certain things are formed naturally via narratives. For selective appropriation, it means the inevitability to exclude or withhold some elements of events in the construction of a narrative.

The four core features exemplified above have opened up space for integrating narrative theory with translation studies. Following “the narrative paradigm” (Fisher 1984, 74), Baker (2006, 106) views translation as (re)framing, “an active activity that implies agency and by means of which we consciously participate in the construction of reality”. In other words, translators can utilise various routines or strategies to actively (re)frame specific narratives. This marks the narrative approach in translation or the socio-narrative theory (Harding 2012a, 2012b). As regards this theory, it is believed that “framing” (more related to the textual level) and “re-narration” (more related to the contextual level) are the two “socio-narrative toolkits” (Hermans *et al.* 2022, 16) and the two terms themselves identify how translation is at play in constructing reality of narratives. In this context, translation can be understood as an act of (re)-narration, a process that “constructs rather than represents events and characters it re-narrates in another language” (Baker 2014, 159), but (re)framing is the means by which narratives are constructed in translation.

Pursuant to the features of narratives, Baker (2006, 112) proposes four major devices used to (re)frame narratives of ST in translation, although she admits the list of such devices is “open-ended” and “inevitably illustrative rather than comprehensive”. They are temporal and

spatial framing, framing through selective appropriation, framing by labelling and repositioning of participants.

First and foremost, temporal and spatial framing means embedding a particular text in a specific temporal and spatial context so as to establish links between narratives in the text and current narratives familiar to the audiences.

Second, selective appropriation involves accentuating or suppressing certain aspects of narratives encoded in textual materials or ST by adding or deleting certain parts of original narratives, which usually includes two ways: higher-level pattern of selectivity (of specific texts, authors, languages and cultures) and pattern of selectivity within the text.

Third, framing by labelling is a discursive process in which a term or phrase is adopted to identify certain key elements in narratives, which is demonstrably the case of names and titles.

Last, reposition of participants means changing the relationship among participants of translation or that between participants and potential readers by manipulating or altering the configuration of the positions of time, space, dialects, registers etc., which is usually achieved in paratextual commentaries and within the TT itself.

4. CASE STUDY: TRANSLATING *PLANET EARTH III* FOR CHINESE AUDIENCES

When it comes to translating narratives in videos or films, particularly those in nature documentaries, the last three devices are resorted to. As they belong to “a broader range of contexts and genres” (Baker 2017, 190), nature documentaries in general tend to lend themselves to narrative analysis since they are multimodal resources and narratives encoded are indeed edited, at least in some ways, to raise ecological awareness of the public. So when translating narratives as such, reframing activities does happen, except that temporal and spatial framing is often excluded because the context and purpose of both original and re-narrated narratives is usually the same.

Multimodal translation techniques could be applied in framing through selective appropriation and repositioning of participants, while reframing by labelling is often used in title translation. Overall, reframing devices can also be reciprocal and consistent in nature.

Observing the reframed narratives in *Diqiumaidong III 地球脉动第三季*, the paper intends to analyse how framing through selective appropriation, framing by labelling and repositioning of participants are achieved in TT and how ecological narratives are reinterpreted for the Chinese audiences. To ensure accuracy in analyses, all the data examined are obtained from the word-for-word transcript of ST and TT.

4.1 Framing through Selective Appropriation

By selective appropriation, it actually means, in the context of the third season, “inclusion and exclusion of specific texts, authors, languages or cultures” exhibited in the ST (Baker 2006, 114). Four examples are provided, two dedicated to inclusion and two exclusion in order to illustrate the very reframing device.

Amplification is adopted in narratives either to provide information or to highlight certain scenarios. On the one hand, feeding audiences with extra information is a way for knowledge acquisition. In *Example 1*, only common names are mentioned in ST since referring to binomial names⁷ in Latin can be tedious and troublesome.

But since these binomials are translated into Chinese, short academic names are derived. In transposing these concepts, the TT provides both common names “海天使 sea angel” “海蝴蝶 sea butterfly”, which are also strengthened by visuality presented in video, and academic names pursuant to Latin “裸海蝶 *clione limacina*” “翼足螺 *limacina helicina*”, which are more professional as a nature documentary. In so doing, the Chinese audiences are equipped with knowledge of the species and the documentary is construed as high quality.

Example 1

ST: A sea angel... and there are other hungry arrivals. A sea butterfly. A snail with wings. (Planet Earth III “Coasts” 14:00-14:53)

TT: 这是一只裸海蝶, 又名冰海天使.....其他饥肠辘辘的访客也来了。这是翼足螺, 又名海蝴蝶, 它长得像一只长着翅膀的蜗牛。(Diqiumaidong III “Hailuzhijian” 14:00-14:53)

MT⁸: This is a *clione limacina*(*naked sea butterfly*), also known as sea angel in icy waters ... and other hungry visitors have arrived. This is a *limacina helicina*(*pteropod snail*), also known as sea butterfly, which looks like a snail with wings.

On the other hand, by adding utterances highlighting the extremity of natural disasters, TT can appeal to the audiences and urge them to right their wrongs. In *Example 2*, addition is mostly demonstrated by the four-character idiom “遮天蔽日”, which to some extent equals “overcast”, meaning covering the sky and sun because of vast numbers. It is used to overstate the extremity of a perilous situation.

Here it is added to highlight the severity of the desert locust plague in Northern Africa, which is brought by heavy rainfall in such an arid place due to climate change. Therefore, by adding tragic information of the plague, TT brings the audiences to the presence of human-wildlife conflicts caused by global warming, who is also our wrongdoing.

Example 2

ST: Swarms merge and they become a plague. (Planet Earth III “Human” 39:40-39:45)

TT: 成群的沙漠蝗虫遮天蔽日, 造成蝗灾。(Diqiumaidong III “Yurengongwu” 39:40-39:45)

MT: Swarms of desert locusts cover the sky and sun, causing a locust plague.

In addition, certain information encoded in ST narratives are deleted to ensure popularity of the Chinese-edited season. For one thing, some over-professional statements are blurred. In *Example 3*, detailed descriptions of ocean currents are deleted.

No longer defined as “some of the most powerful of all”, the very current here the California Current⁹ is reframed as “强大的洋流”, meaning powerful currents. This is understandable since the audiences are no geography expert and the extra modification (laid yet without introducing other powerful currents) may be superfluous.

Example 3

ST: Here on Canada's west coast, some of the most powerful of all ocean currents deliver a constant supply of nutrients to the shores of countless islands. (Planet Earth III "Coasts" 27:52-28:05)

TT: 在加拿大西海岸，强大的洋流源源不断地将营养物质输送至众多岛屿的岸边。(Diqiumaidong III "Hailuzhijian" 27:52-28:05)

MT: On Canada's west coast, strong ocean currents continuously transport nutrients to the shores of numerous islands.

For another, deletion is sought when it is hard to introduce a new culturally-connotated concept for foreign audiences. In *Example 4*, the concept of "demi-god", or called minor god, literally meaning a being with lesser divine status than a god, represents the Hindu people's attitude to cobras, something worthy of godly respect yet still ranked between humans and gods. For the Chinese audiences, it is a brand-new concept and translating it literally might complicate narrativity. So TT partially deletes the prefix of the word and simply renders it as "神明" to avoid cultural misunderstandings and communication failure.

Example 4

ST: They have found a home where the Hindu villagers revere them and consider them to be demi-gods. (Planet Earth III "Human" 18:22-18:32)

TT: 印度村庄给孟加拉眼镜蛇提供了栖息之所，当地的村民会对他们敬若神明。(Diqiumaidong III "Yurengongwu" 18:15-18:32)

MT: Indian villages provide a habitat for Bengal cobras, which are revered as gods by local villagers.

4.2 Framing by Labelling

Apart from names which are normally part of a rival system due to the existence of counter-naming¹⁰, titles of textual or visual products, films in particular, can also be reframed through labelling to distribute new narratives for the target audiences. Although Zhang & Osborne (2025) believes in analysing film title translation through the features of narratives, framing by labelling still offers insights into this field. Film titles represent the very first-hand information presented to potential audiences (Fakharzadeh 2022). When it comes to translating film titles, that first-hand information needs to be adapted into another market for audiences who speak different another language. In that process, necessarily involved are discursive choices, which are subject to "a range of socio-economic factors" (Zhang & Osborne 2025, 28). The very discursive choices are, however, achieved through labelling, or "using a lexical item, term or phrase to identify a person, place, group, event or any other key elements in a narrative" (Baker 2006, 122).

In the case of *Planet Earth* series, the title of the nature documentary franchise is translated as *Diqiumaidong* 地球脉动 in Chinese, which means the pulsations of the planet earth. By so doing, the earth is personified in the new narrative of TT. Equipped with vital signs of pulsations, the earth is no longer viewed as a static and lifeless sphere. Rather, it is treated as a living organism, whose blood pulses through her veins, though metaphorically, as those of any

other living creatures including humans. That is to say, if the earth has blood and veins, we humans and other living species, animals or plants, can be deemed as cells of her body. The vicissitudes and welfare of lives on the planet has direct yet profound implications on her as cancers do to any living creatures. Also, by using the term *maidong* 脉动, the film can be linked with a famous vitamin beverage¹¹ with the same name in China and the Chinese film title becomes a four-character idiom, which is more vivid and persuasive in the Chinese culture. Through a quotation of a familiar narrative, which emphasises health and sports, and persistence to the Chinese literary tradition, the Chinese audiences become more easily satisfied with the film title and the popularity¹² of the documentary can be ascribed, at least partly, to the translation of the very title. But it should also be noted that adding the term *maidong* 脉动 is an act of selective appropriation as well, which means the devices of reframing narratives can sometimes overlap.

In terms of *Diqiumaidong III 地球脉动第三季*, the titles of all eight episodes are translated as four-character idioms in Chinese as demonstrated in **Table 1: The Episode Titles of Planet Earth III and their Chinese version**. The narratives are re-narrated in a way that harmony without uniformity is achieved.

Table 1: The Episode Titles of Planet Earth III and their Chinese versions

S & E ¹³	ST Titles	TT Titles ¹⁴	Meanings of TT Titles ¹⁵
S3E1	Coasts	海陆之间	Between Land and Sea
S3E2	Ocean	波涛之下	Beneath the Waves
S3E3	Deserts & Grasslands	广袤之地	Vast Land
S3E4	Freshwater	滴水之源	Fountainhead of Freshwater
S3E5	Forests	林木之中	Among the Trees
S3E6	Extremes	极端之境	Extreme Realm
S3E7	Human	与人共舞	Dancing with Humans
S3E8	Heroes	家园卫士	Home Guardians

For one, certain characteristics of narratives encoded in ST are preserved. Paramount of all, it can be noted that all the titles are dealt with in strict accordance with their original properties. Except the last two titles, which point to the roles of humans, the other titles in ST refer specifically to the different habitats of various wildlife.

When translated into Chinese, they still preserve their identities as natural places, signalled by the third character of idioms “zhi之” in TT, which is an auxiliary word sometimes without actual meanings but indicative of affiliation. So by using “zhi之”, the Chinese audiences can quickly understand that the characters before “zhi之” are habitats where wildlife live while the one after “zhi之” represents the status of these habitats, i.e. their locations, properties, importance. In structure, narratives are reframed by labelling the character “zhi之” and transformed to fit the Chinese literary appetites.

On the other hand, the last two episodes “Human” and “Heroes” are reframed by labelling the characters “人ren” and “卫士weishi”, referring respectively to humans and guardians. Similar to narratives in ST, the role of humans is underlined as the season reflects on “the resilience and adaptability of nature” and the evolution of her subjects as to changing their lives

to meet “the challenges of a rapidly changing world dominated more than ever by a powerful force: us” (BBC 2023).

For another, these new Chinese titles encompass in their narratives inspiring new ideas as to the relations between wildlife and their habitats and between humans and nature. First, new cultural connotations are attached represented by E3, E4 and E6, as the character “zhi之” equals, more or less, the function of “of” in English. In E3, “广袤之地”, vast land or the land of breadth and length in Chinese, is translated from “Deserts & Grasslands”, whose territories combine both wilderness and rich soil. Instead of focusing on different environments where wildlife call home, the Chinese version reiterates the vast landscape of the two types of habitats and highlights the adaptability of different species on different but vast places. In E4, “Freshwater” is rendered as “滴水之源”, or Fountainhead of Freshwater, which stresses the importance of freshwater source. In China, there goes a proverb “a drop of water shall be returned with a burst of spring¹⁶”, indicating freshwater as source of life. By appealing to the proverb, narratives are reframed with a bid to stressing freshwater as source of all animals on earth. In E6, “Extremes” is reframed as “极端之境”, which means Extreme Realm or the Kingdom of Extremity. In this sense, those extreme places are compared metaphorically to a realm and the dwellers on it must work and toil extremely hard to outlive the tyranny of the cruel monarch, the harsh environment where food is scarce and work time is long.

Second, the focus of certain titles shifts from natural habitats to the inhabitants as are the cases of E1, E2, and E5. In these cases, the character “zhi之” has no actual meaning but indicates affiliation between the places (海陆land and see, 波涛waves, 林木tress) and the prepositions of direction (间between, 下beneath, 中among). Therefore, the three titles (Coasts, Ocean, Forests) are translated respectively as “海陆之间” “波涛之下” “林木之中”, which means in Chinese: Between Land and Sea, Beneath the Waves and Among the Trees. Not only are they visualised and poetic pictures, they also brings the inhabitants living among them into the audience attention, as the latter would, first and foremost, be captivated by the fascinating titles and ask themselves a question, that is, who lives between, beneath and among those places.

Last, the role of humans is no longer stated alone, but in line with wildlife, as evidence by E7 and E8. In E7, the title “Human” is translated as “与人共舞”, meaning “Dancing with Humans” in Chinese. Here comes the question. Who would do so? In this context, definitely the very wildlife presented. So instead of stressing the presence of humans, this narrative reaccentuates the harmonious existence between humans and animals. This can be proven by such a scene where a rhino is walking on the streets of Sauraha, Nepal simply to find food while local people are not astonished but busy picturing the unique moment (Planet Earth III “Human” 00:33-02:15). In E8, “Heroes”, referring to scientists, activists and volunteers dedicated to wildlife protection and ecological cause, are rendered as “家园卫士”, meaning Home Guardians in Chinese. This explicates and manifests the planet earth as home to all species and explicitates the contribution of humans as vital in safeguarding the security and welfare of all species on earth.

In general, through framing by labelling, the episode titles of *Planet Earth III* are endowed with new narratives that attract wider attention from the Chinese audiences. Ecological narratives of the titles, re-narrated in their own ways, not only earn wide popularity among its Chinese followers, but also urge the target language receptors to reflect on broader issues concerning nature, wildlife and humanities.

4.3 Repositioning of Participants

As indicated by relationality, one narrativity feature of utmost importance, participants in translation (including but not limited to the narrator vs. the narrated, the translator vs. the translated, the hearer vs. the heard) can be repositioned in relation to one another or to the TT audiences through altering the linguistic devices in ST or resorting to means of self- and other identification (Baker 2006, 132). Via nuanced adjustment, or what Baker would call “very subtle choices”, of those linguistic parameters, the relations among those participants can be realigned or reframed in narratives in terms of “time and social/political space” (Ibid). In *Planet Earth III*, reposition of participants can be seen in the translated texts and utterances narrated by Sir David, in which textual features are renegotiated to “reconfigure the relationship between participants within or around the source narrative” (Ibid: 135).

First and foremost, reposition of participants can help reveal or explicitate hidden relations in the original narratives by using obvious words. As can be shown by *Example 5*, the pup, referring to a young Cape fur seal, is no doubt a marine animal. Since it is natural to resort to euphemism in English, the original narrative does not elaborate on the exact habitat, but renders it as “where this pup belongs”. When distributed and translated in a multimodal manner, the scene of the pup, however, is followed by the scene of vast oceans. So it is self-evident that the exact living zone “大海”, or the sea, can be used to supplement as a practice of visual translation, making explicit the relationship between the pup and its natural habitat filmed in the video. In the same vein, explicitation can also be observed in the rendering of cobras, notorious poisonous snakes that have claimed the lives of many. Since they are infamous for killing people, the sentence “your reputation precedes you” (Planet Earth III “Human” 13:42-13:51), used to describe them, are translated as “恶名在外” (Diqiumaidong III “Yurengongwu” 13:42-13:51), meaning “have a bad reputation”, which points to the wickedness of ferocious species directly for the audiences.

Example 5

ST: There is no question as to where this pup belongs. (Planet Earth III “Coasts” 05:52-05:56)

TT: 显然, 这只南非海狗幼崽属于大海。(Diqiumaidong III “Hailuzhijian” 海 05:52-05:56)

MT: Clearly, this Cape fur seal pup belongs in the sea.

Second, it can personify wildlife as participants and empathy can thus be achieved. In *Example 6*, the flamingo colony is inflicted by a devastatingly annual hurricane which is arriving earlier every year. In that situation, the lives of newly-hatched chicks are at risk. To stress the role of grown flamingos, they are called “adults” in the original narrative and their endeavour to save the chicks “bailing out”, which put them in the shoes of human parents who come to their children’s aid in dark days.

When it comes to weaving new narratives in TT, the “adults” are referred more directly and specifically as “父母”, or “parents” and their “bailing out” activities, literally meaning aiding financially, are contextualised as “拯救”, or “save”. By so doing, the personification of flamingos in the reframed ecological narrative allows the TT audiences to empathise their natural behaviours and stand in awe of them as great parents who protect their offsprings in harm’s way.

Example 6

ST: The adults do what they can bailing out their nests, but they can only do so much.
(Planet Earth III “Coasts” 40:20-40:44)

TT: 加勒比海红鹤父母尽可能地拯救鸟巢，但它们能做的很有限。
(Diqiumaidong III “Hailuzhijian” 40:20-40:44)

MT: Caribbean flamingo parents try their best to save the nest, but there are limits as to what they can do.

Third, the register of narratives can be adapted for different purposes through repositioning of participants. For instance, narratives in *Example 7* are reframed for dramatic effects. While narrating bears searching for food in a town near Lake Tahoe in North America, Sir David tries to be humourous and a drama can be deduced from his usage of two interrogative sentence. In the translated version, drama is created, however, through nuanced adjustment in register. Instead of depicting bears as common Gypsy-like scavengers, evidenced by “gorge” “takeaway” “just want to dine in”, bears in the eyes of the Chinese audiences are shaped as slightly poetic elves, who can to the town occasionally for “美味的餐点”, meaning a delicious meal, instead of take-aways, normally fast food (even if they do eat fast food according to the video).

Example 7

ST: This is the great place to gorge... Why struggle for a meal when you can cross the street for a takeaway? ... But why stop here? Some bears just want to dine in.
(Planet Earth III “Human” 24:24-25:20)

TT: 这里可以享受到大量的食物.....何必还要费力捕食呢，穿越街道就能轻松找到美味的餐点.....当然它们没有止步于此，一些美洲美熊也想进屋里来用餐。(Diqiumaidong III “Yurengongwu” 24:24-25: 20)

MT: There is plenty of food to enjoy here ...why bother hunting when you can easily find a delicious meal just by walking across the street ... of course, they do not stop there, some American bears also want to come into the house to eat.

Narratives can also be academic, which is especially so in introducing the names of species. In Episode Six Extremes, when introducing endemic species of Hang Sơn Đoòng , Vietnam, “translucent cave fish and shrimps” are translated as “韩松洞中半透明的洞穴盲鱼” (Planet Earth III “Extremes” 04:30-04:35; Diqiumaidong III “Jiduanzhijing” 04:30-04:35), meaning “blind cave fish and swarm shrimp in Hang Sơn Đoòng”. To propagate knowledge of these species, the TT refuses generalisation in the original narratives and grasps the very

features of the species by “盲blind” and “沼swarm” respectively. Last but not least, narratives are reframed by appealing to familiar concepts of TT audiences. In *Example 8*, the Vietnamese heroine Trang Nguyen infiltrates the illegal ivory trade in Cote d’Ivoire by posing as a buyer. In this scene, while helping local police in capturing illegal traders, she acts an interested buyer and spy and pretends to be captured as well to avoid revenge. The phrase “cover story” here is reinterpreted as “马脚”, similar to “the cloven foot” but not necessarily negative in meanings, a common metaphor in the Chinese culture. Instead of elaborating on the definition of cover story, the TT familiarise the audiences with common Chinese idioms, which also highlights the heroic achievement of Nguyen in protecting wildlife and appeals to the public to follow her deeds and spirits, or at least try to.

Example 8

ST: For her own safety, she has to keep her cover story and behave as a criminal. (Planet Earth III “Heroes” 24:22-24:46)

TT: 为了她自身的安全, 阮庄 (Trang Nguyen) 不能露出任何马脚, 她必须表现得和真正的犯罪分子一样。(Diqiumaidong III “Jiayuanweishi” 24:22-24:46)

MT: For her own safety, Trang Nguyen must show the cloven foot and act like a true criminal.

In a nutshell, through repositioning of participants, the Chinese audiences are more engaged in a world desperate for wildlife conservation. By “creat(ing) distance or on the contrary closeness” (Mason & Şerban 2003, 290) between the audiences and the translation and between the audiences and the narrated, repositioning of participants offers an insight into how humans should care, value and work to protect the wonders of nature.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Through detailed analyses of narrative reframing strategies above, it can be noted that the three different reframing devices are all suitable for retelling ecological narratives but are applicable in different and specific situations. Selective appropriation, epitomised by addition and deletion, are quite useful in tackling cases where there exists additional or inadequate information, be they textual, linguistic, conceptual or cultural. Unlike the previous one, repositioning of participants within textual materials focuses primarily on the configuration of relations among translator, translated text, narrator, narrated wildlife and audiences. This can be achieved via explicitation, empathy, personification, analogy, cultural substitution among various means. The only difference from selective appropriation is that information is processed and contextualised accordingly but direct amplification and omission are usually neglected. Reframing by labelling in this context, nevertheless, concentrates on the nuanced differences of narrativity concealed in both ST and TT. It can be seen through this device that the interplay of overlapping reframing tactics do sometimes exist.

Altogether, these devices adopted in *Diqiumaidong III 地球脉动第三季* contribute to the formation of re-narrated narratives, or reinterpretations of the natural world from the Chinese perspective. On the one hand, the new Chinese edition, a multimodally-translated version, conveys to the Chinese audiences general ideas and visualised news as to how wildlife survives and thrives in their natural habitats and how they adapt to the ever-changing world. In the

process, information distributed is filtered and re-edited so that it becomes easily acceptable in the transnational context. On the other hand, stories retold via audio-visual translation also raise the alarm for humanities at large. Through re-narration, the Chinese audiences are exposed to the most severe and imminent of problems. Environmental degradation, global warming, climate change, rise of sea levels, human-wildlife conflict, poaching, deforestation, species extinction and many other urgent issues are revealed to us by sheer force of narratives encoded in the stories of wildlife. Combined with audio-visual materials, narrativity, in line with translation, has found its way into ecological discourses, both global and local. Hopefully, translation as story-telling in transnational contexts can raise people's awareness of environmental protection and harmonious coexistence and, with a word of caution, encourages some to act in bravery.

Funding

This research receives no specific grant from any funding agency.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interests is to be declared.

Footnotes

- 1) *The Blue Planet* is nature documentary series co-produced by the BBC Natural History Unit and Discovery Channel and narrated by Sir David Attenborough. The executive producer is Alastair Fothergill. Premiered in 2001 in the United Kingdom, the series has spawned two series and several films as of 2017.
- 2) Lorraine Heggessey (1956-) is a British television producer and executive, who was the first woman to serve as Controller of BBC One (2000-2005), the BBC'S primary TV channel. Both *The Blue Planet* and *Planet Earth* were commission during her term of office.
- 3) Sir David Attenborough (1926-) is a British broadcaster, biologist, natural historian and writer. He is widely considered as father of modern nature documentaries and a national treasure in the UK. His filmography as a writer, presenter and narrator has spanned eight decades, represented by nine nature documentary series including *The Blue Planet*, *Planet Earth*. Although his earlier work focused more on the wonders of nature, his later work has been dedicated to environmental causes. First knighted by the Queen ElizabethII in 1985, he has been awarded in his life time many prizes and titles, including Champion of the Earth, Emmy Awards for Outstanding Narration, UK's Favourite TV Presenter of All Time etc.
- 4) This refers to *Planet Earth: Hostile Paradise or Perfect Hell (2024)*. It is a re-cut edition from *Planet Earth III* and was granted a slot for a national release across cinemas from 27 July, 2024, distributed by China Film Co. It is viewed as the BBC's ambition for the Chinese box-office.
- 5) Docu TV is the documentary channel of Shanghai Media Group. Founded in 2002, the channel has an interested area, covering history, humanities & arts, nature etc.
- 6) Liu Cong (1989-), or 刘琮 in Chinese, is a Chinese voice actor and a senior dubbing director. His representative works include *The Wandering Earth (2019)*, *Dynasties (2019, Chinese Version)* etc.

- 7) It refers to naming species of living things by giving each a name composed of two parts, both of which use Latin grammatical forms. See in Wikipedia https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Binomial_nomenclature.
- 8) A machine-translated version, hereinafter abbreviated as MT, is provided for better understandings. The author has examined the veracity of materials provided.
- 9) It is a powerful cold-water Pacific Ocean current that moves southward along the western coast of North America.
- 10) It refers to the activist's response to the systemic use of euphemisms in the political sphere. For example, FBI (Federal Bureau of Investigation) could be counter-named by some as Federal Bureau of Intimidation. See in Baker *Conflict 1st edition* pp.123.
- 11) The English name of the beverage is Mizone, mimicking its Chinese pronunciation “Maidong脉动”. Founded in 2003, it is a leader in the everyday hydration segment.
- 12) According to Douban, the Chinese counterpart of IMDb, the three seasons of Planet Earth are rated out of ten respectively: 9.7, 9.8, 9.7, earning themselves a place among the most popular nature documentaries in China.
- 13) Here season and episode are abbreviated as S and E respectively.
- 14) In citations, they are presented by the Chinese alphabets *Pinyin*.
- 15) For meanings of TT titles, the draft is provided by Google Translate (see <https://translate.google.com/>) and is post-edited and proof-read into the version above by the author.
- 16) It refers to the Chinese proverb “滴水之恩，当涌泉相报”，which emphasises the importance of repaying one's kindness. Freshwater is used metaphorically here since a drop of water is even very precious as drops of water, when gathered, will finally form a stream.

References

- 1) Baker, Mona. 2006. *Translation and Conflict: A Narrative Account 1st Edition*. London: Routledge.
- 2) Baker, Mona. 2010. “Narratives of Terrorism and Security: ‘Accurate’ Translations, Suspicious Frames.” *Critical Studies on Terrorism* 3(3): 347–64. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17539153.2010.521639>
- 3) Baker, Mona. 2014. “Translation as Re-narration.” In *Translation: A Multidisciplinary Approach*, edited by Juliane House, 158-177. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- 4) Baker, Mona. 2017. “Narrative Analysis and Translation.” In *The Routledge Handbook of Translation Studies and Linguistics*, edited by Kirsten Malmkjaer, 179-193. London: Routledge.
- 5) Baker, Mona. 2018. *Translation and Conflict: A Narrative Account 2nd Edition*. London: Routledge.
- 6) BBC. 2023. “Sir David Attenborough's *Planet Earth III* – ‘We Must Now Look at the World through a New Lens’”. BBC Media Centre. <https://www.bbc.com/mediacentre/mediapacks/planet-earth-3-sir-david-attenborough>

- 7) Delabastita, Dirk. 1989. "Translation and Mass-Communication: Film and TV Translation as Evidence of Cultural Dynamics." *Babel* (35): 193–218.
<https://doi.org/10.1075/babel.35.4.02del>
- 8) Diqiumaidong III *地球脉动第三季*, season 3, episode 1, "Hailuzhijian" *海陆之间*, translated from Planet Earth III "Coasts", narrated by Liu Cong. Aired 29 October, 2023 on Docu TV.
- 9) Diqiumaidong III *地球脉动第三季*, season 3, episode 6, "Jiduanzhijing" *极端之境*, translated from Planet Earth III "Extremes", narrated by Liu Cong. Aired n.d. 2023 on Docu TV.
- 10) Diqiumaidong III *地球脉动第三季*, season 3, episode 7, "Jiayuanweishi" *家园卫士*, translated from Planet Earth III "Heroes", narrated by Liu Cong. Aired n.d. 2023 on Docu TV.
- 11) Diqiumaidong III *地球脉动第三季*, season 3, episode 8, "Yurengongwu" *与人共舞*, translated from Planet Earth III "Human", narrated by Liu Cong. Aired n.d. 2023 on Docu TV.
- 12) Fakharzadeh, Mehrnoosh. 2022. "A Sociological Approach to Official and Non-Official Audiovisual Translators' Practice in Iran: The Case of Movie Title Translation." *Journal of Intercultural Communication Research* 51(4): 430–49.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/17475759.2021.1966075>
- 13) Fisher, Walter R. 1984. "The Narrative Paradigm: in the Beginning". *Journal of Communication* 34(1): 74-87. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.1984.tb02986.x>
- 14) Gambier, Yves. 2003. "Introduction: Screen Transadaptation: Perception and Reception." *The Translator* (2): 171–189.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13556509.2003.10799152>
- 15) Harding, Sue-Ann. 2012a. "Beslan: Six Stories of the Siege." Manchester and NY: Manchester University Press.
- 16) Harding, Sue-Ann. 2012b. "How do I Apply Narrative Theory." *Target* 24(2): 286-309.
<https://doi.org/10.1075/target.24.2.04har>
- 17) Hermans, Theo, Sue-Ann Harding and Julie Boéri. 2022. "A Conversation about Narrative and Translation." *Cultus* (15): 16-39.
- 18) Lopez, German. 2017. "The tricks that nature documentaries use to keep you watching". Vox. <https://www.vox.com/culture/2017/4/29/15470180/nature-documentaries-tricks-fake-sound>
- 19) Mason, Ian, and Adriana Șerban. 2003. "Deixis as an Interactive Feature in Literary Translations from Romanian into English." *Target* 15(2): 269-294.
<https://doi.org/10.1075/target.15.2.04mas>
- 20) Munday, Jeremy, Sara Ramos Pinto, and Jacob Blakesley. 2022. *Introducing Translation Studies, 5th edition*. London: Routledge.

- 21) *Planet Earth III*, season 3, episode 1, “Coasts”, narrated by David Attenborough. Aired 22 October, 2023, on BBC. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/programmes/m001rswk>
- 22) *Planet Earth III*, season 3, episode 6, “Extremes”, narrated by David Attenborough. Aired 26 November, 2023, on BBC. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/programmes/m001sxm6>
- 23) *Planet Earth III*, season 3, episode 7, “Human”, narrated by David Attenborough. Aired 3 December, 2023, on BBC. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/programmes/m001t485>
- 24) *Planet Earth III*, season 3, episode 8, “Heroes”, narrated by David Attenborough. Aired 10 December, 2023, on BBC. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/programmes/m001tchh>
- 25) Slenske, Michael. 2007. “Alastair Fothergill - Planet Earth – TV”. The New York Times. <https://www.nytimes.com/2007/03/18/arts/television/18slen.html>
- 26) Somers, Margaret R. 1992. “Narrativity, Narrative Identity, and Social Action: Rethinking English Working-Class Formation.” *Social Science History* 16(4):591-630. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1171314>
- 27) Somers, Margaret R. 1997. “Deconstructing and Reconstructing Class Formation Theory: Narrativity, Relational Analysis, and Social Theory.” In *Reworking Class*, edited by John R. Hall, 73-106. Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press
- 28) Somers, Margaret R., and Gloria Gibson. 1994. “Reclaiming the Epistemological ‘Other’: Narrative and the Social Constitution of Identity.” In *Social Theory and the Politics of Identity*, edited by Craig Calhoun, 37–99. Cambridge, Manchester & Oxford: Blackwell.
- 29) Zhang, Qi, and Caitríona Osborne. 2025. “Narratives in Film Title Translation: A Study of Films by Zhang Yimou and Jia Zhangke.” *Translation Spaces* 14(1): 25-49. <https://doi.org/10.1075/ts.24005.zha>